

PROCRASTINATION AND ITS IMPACT ON QUALITY OF LIFE

Khusainova Firuza Tokhirovna

Associate Professor of General Sciences and Culture Department of
Tashkent State University of Law
fayruzakhusainova@gmail.com
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Abstract: The reasons for the growth of procrastination, the dangerous aspects of postponing things, types of procrastination, as well as ways to solve this phenomenon are considered.

Key words: procrastination, self-control, chaos, personality, emotional burnout, discomfort, time management.

Procrastination is the unhealthy putting off of important things, tasks and responsibilities until later.

Today there is a clear increase in procrastination in all spheres of human activity, and many people face this problem. Postponing things until later is common to almost all people, but when it comes to chronic procrastination, a person puts things off, even if he is completely sure of their necessity and importance. He understands that this is necessary and useful, and that the plan must be realized. However, he deliberately postpones the implementation of the plan, despite the possible problems and complications. Instead of focusing on truly important tasks, he focuses on small and insignificant matters.

There are several ways to explain the reasons for this phenomenon. This is due to the insignificance or excessive importance of the task, its boring, meaninglessness, excessive complexity, large amounts of time, unattractiveness, as well as bad mood or laziness.

When procrastinating, self-control decreases and a person loses his energy. The less energy left, the greater the chances of postponing the task indefinitely and doing nothing again. Without making efforts to achieve personal goals, a person misses the opportunity to enrich his life.

Scientist Luchenkova M.A. in his monograph he notes that procrastination not only brings chaos into the living space of an individual, but also significantly blocks the realization of potential. In fact, progressive development is being replaced by regressive development.

According to the author of the article “Theoretical foundations for studying the phenomenon of procrastination” V.S. Kovylin, the main signs of procrastination are the lack of productivity and meaning in the actions performed, coupled with the constant postponement of what is really important and useful. To a certain extent there is nothing wrong with this, since no person can work like a machine. Short rest breaks and changes in activity have a beneficial effect on overall productivity. Therefore, another sign of procrastination is negative consequences, such as violation of deadlines, failure of planned projects, general dissatisfaction with one’s professional activities, and possible personal and psychological problems in this regard.

But the most dangerous thing is that our procrastination can turn into a normal state in which we spend most of our time. Everything important is put off until later; sometimes, due to deadlines, you have to abandon what you planned or do it quickly in an impossibly short period of time. This leads to negative consequences, such as emotional burnout, decreased self-esteem, troubles at work, missed opportunities, health problems, etc.

Many researchers highlight the negative consequences of procrastination. Psychologist Leo Babaut notes the following dangerous aspects of procrastination:

We see that procrastination is accompanied by internal discomfort and leads to negative consequences.

You can also mention the research of N. Milgram, who divided procrastination into the following types:

Everyday procrastination

Thoughts constantly flash in a person's head that a task needs to be completed. However, procrastination gets in the way. He believes that any matter can be put on a shelf and forgotten

Procrastination in decision making

A person is afraid to make decisions, which prevents him from setting goals and achieving results. He simply cannot reach his potential. This condition arises due to fear of change

Compulsive procrastination

A person puts things off and is too afraid to make an important decision

Neurotic procrastination

Fear of change. The person does not notice and does not control his condition: the heartbeat increases, involuntary trembling, nervous tic - he gets scared and cannot act

Academic procrastination

Preparation for a session is put off by a person until the last moment, which he later regrets

Procrastination thus leads to unproductive implementation of desired plans.

How to beat procrastination? Of course, each person can decide for himself whether to live with procrastination or give it up. If you fight it, then you need to learn how to properly manage your time - prioritize all existing tasks, do not waste your time on useless things, work on strong-willed qualities, try to bring things to the end, developing self-discipline and perseverance, understanding that every completed task brings self-confidence, and also forms the habit of finishing what you start.

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